

Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Methyl-2 (2-Methyl-4-Hydroxy-5-Isopropyl)-Phenyl-3-Aryl-5-H/ Methyl-4'-Thiazolidinones

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4-Thiazolidinones were prepared by the action of thioglycolic acid or thioleptic acid on Schiff bases which were obtained from 4-acetothymol and different aromatic bases. The constitution was supported by uv and ir spectra. Products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

THYMOL derivatives possess antituberculostatic¹, antileprotic², anthelmintic³, antimicrobial activity⁴, and are also antiseptics⁵. 4-Thiazolidinone are also associated with various kind of biological activities like hypnotic⁶, anaesthetic⁷, antifungal⁸ etc. With a view to get more active drug products we have prepared 4-Thiazolidinone of type (I) by the action of thioglycolic acid or thioleptic acid on Schiff bases which were obtained by condensing 4-acetothymol with different aromatic bases. The constitution was supported by uv and ir spectra. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

Where R = Substituted phenyl
R' = H or CH₃

UV and IR spectra

The uv spectra of 4-thiazolidinone were taken using ethanol as solvent. Three bands were obtained

at $\lambda_{\max}$ 215, 230 and 280 mu, the last being the characteristic of 4-thiazolidinone¹¹. The ir spectra were taken on KBr pellets and characterised. The $>C=O$ group frequency was obtained at 1680 cm^{-1} , $CO-N<$ at 1580 cm^{-1} and phenolic OH at 3300 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

1) Preparation of 2-Methyl-4-hydroxy-5-isopropyl acetophenone : (4-Acetothymol) :

It was prepared by condensing thymol with acetyl chloride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride using nitrobenzene as solvent⁹.

2) Preparation of 2-Methyl-4-hydroxy-5-isopropyl acetophenone anils :

The anils were prepared by using Reddellien method¹². 4-Acetothymol (0.01 mole) was condensed with different aromatic amines (0.011 mole) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g at 160°) for 2 hrs. The temperature was then raised to 180° for 5 mts. The products were isolated using chloroform as solvent and crystallised from ethanol (Physical constants are recorded in Table 1).

TABLE-1. PHYSICAL CONSTANT OF ANILS

Sr. No.	R	Formula	Yield in %	m p. °C	% of Nitrogen calculated	found
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ON	55	93	5.24	5.20
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON	51	120	4.98	4.93
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON	49	105	4.98	4.93
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON	49	70	4.98	4.93
5.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ OCIN	53	90	4.64	4.60
6.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ OCIN	49	125	4.64	4.60
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ OCIN	54	110	4.64	4.60
8.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ BrON	52	115	4.20	4.16
9.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	50	100	4.71	4.67
10.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	46	85	4.71	4.67
11.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂	43	85	8.97	8.90
12.	α -Naphthyl	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ ON ₂	41	107	6.83	6.80

3) Preparation of 2'-methyl-2°-(2-methyl-4-hydroxy-5-isopropyl)-phenyl 3'-aryl-5-H|methyl-4'-thiazolidinone :

Thioglycolic acid or thiolactic acid (0.05 mole) was added to the solution of Schiff bases (0.05 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for six hrs.

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TABLE - 2. PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF 4'-THIAZOLIDINONES OF TYPE I

Sr. No.	R	R'	Formula	Yield in %	m.p. °C	% of Nitrogen	
						calculated	found
1.	Phenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ ONS	35	125	4.52	4.50
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ONS	32	110	4.32	4.28
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ONS	30	105	4.32	4.28
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ONS	31	122	4.32	4.28
5.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ClONS	28	100	4.06	4.00
6.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ClONS	30	100	4.06	4.00
7.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ BrONS	33	107	3.60	3.56
8.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂ NS	31	70	4.12	4.10
9.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ S	34	83	7.89	7.85
10.	α -Naphthyl	H	C ₃₀ H ₃₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	30	320d	5.78	5.70
11.	Phenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ONS	33	122	4.32	4.27
12.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ ONS	31	110	4.14	4.10
13.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ ONS	30	105	4.14	4.10
14.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ ONS	31	105	4.14	4.10
15.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ClONS	28	100	3.51	3.45
16.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ClONS	26	100	3.51	3.55
17.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ClONS	28	100	3.51	3.55
18.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ BrONS	32	107	3.48	3.40
19.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂ NS	31	68	3.95	3.90
20.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂ NS	31	75	3.95	3.90

Compound no. 1 and 11 gave correct C, H analysis.

Products were isolated and crystallised from ethanol. (Physical constants are recorded in Table 2).

Antimicrobial Screening

All 4'-thiazolidinones were screened for antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *A. niger* using cub-plate method¹⁰. From the experimental data, it was observed that all products were moderately active against Gram Positive and Gram Negative bacteria.

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